

OUTLINE OF THE PERFORMANCES OF REINFORCED CONCRETE BUILDINGS DURING FEBRUARY 2023 TURKIYE EARTHQUAKES AND POTENTIAL USE OF FRPs TOWARDS MORE RESILIENT BUILDINGS

Caglar Goksu, Istanbul Technical University, Türkiye, goksuc@itu.edu.tr
Bilal Sari, Istanbul Technical University, Türkiye, sarib19@itu.edu.tr
M. Fethi Gullu, Harran University, Türkiye, fethigullu@harran.edu.tr
Kutay Orakcal, Bogazici University, Türkiye, kutay.orakcal@boun.edu.tr
Alper Ilki, Istanbul Technical University, Türkiye, ailki@itu.edu.tr

ABSTRACT

Three consecutive earthquakes (M_w 7.7, 7.6, and 6.4) struck Türkiye in February 2023, impacting 11 provinces with a population of over 16 million. The earthquakes and numerous aftershocks caused widespread devastation, resulting in the collapse or severe damage of over 250,000 buildings. This study presents on-site investigations of the affected buildings, identifying deficiencies and structural failures. It also explores the potential of fiber reinforced polymers for enhancing building resilience, summarizing previous experimental studies and actual applications in the light of the observed damages from the recent February 2023 Türkiye Earthquakes.

KEYWORDS

Earthquake; reconnaissance; reinforced concrete; resilience; retrofitting; seismic.

INTRODUCTION

Türkiye is among the world's earthquake-prone countries, with tens of earthquakes causing over 140,000 casualties and economic losses exceeding \$150 billion from 1900 to the present (Emre et al., 2018, SBO, 2023). The Anatolian Block, encompassing the mainland of Türkiye, is bounded by two significant tectonic structures: the North Anatolian Fault (NAF) to the north and the East Anatolian Fault (EAF) to the southeast. In February 2023, three consecutive earthquakes with moment magnitudes of 7.7, 7.6, and 6.4 struck Türkiye along the EAF (AFAD, 2023). The epicenter of the first earthquake was Kahramanmaraş-Pazarcık, followed by earthquakes with epicenters of Kahramanmaraş-Elbistan and Hatay-Yayladagi for the second and third earthquakes, respectively. These seismic events affected 11 provinces in Türkiye, including Kahramanmaraş, Adiyaman, Hatay, Osmaniye, Gaziantep, Kilis, Sanliurfa, Diyarbakir, Malatya, Adana, and Elazig, with a combined population of over 16 million. The destructive impact resulted in massive collapses and damage to various structures such as buildings, bridges, airports, tunnels, retaining structures, hydraulic structures, and lifelines. Approximately 38,000 buildings collapsed during the earthquakes, with 12,000 of them being reinforced concrete (RC) structures (MoEUCC, 2023). The fatalities in Türkiye surpassed 50,000, and more than 100,000 individuals sustained injuries (AFAD, 2023). It is estimated that the total burden of the disaster caused by the earthquakes on the Turkish economy is approximately 103.6 billion dollars (SBO, 2023). This study primarily focuses on the visual inspection of buildings affected by these earthquakes. The observed damage types were documented, taking into account the strong motion data provided by AFAD, the characteristics of structural systems and construction materials. Additionally, a concise summary of seismic strengthening techniques using fiber reinforced polymers (FRPs) is presented, based on previous experimental studies, along with their potential practical applications, considering the damages observed during the recent February 2023 Earthquakes in Türkiye.

GROUND MOTION INTENSITY MEASURES

Figure 1 provides the characteristics of the three main earthquakes that hit the region in February 2023. These seismic events led to a fault rupture, stretching over 300 km along the left-lateral EAF. The fault slipped approximately 3 to 5 meters during the earthquakes (EERI, 2023).

Figure 1: Three sequential earthquakes and distribution of their aftershocks (modified from AFAD, 2023)

TBEC (2018) defines four distinct levels of earthquake ground motion based on return periods and the corresponding probabilities of exceedance. DD-1, known as the maximum expected earthquake ground motion level, signifies the ground motion anticipated to occur statistically once every 2475 years or with a 2% probability of exceedance within a 50-year span. DD-2 represents the standard design earthquake ground motion level, which corresponds to statistical return period of 475 years or having a 10% probability of exceedance within 50 years. Regarding the acceleration data collected from the strong ground motion stations in the earthquake-affected area, peak ground acceleration (PGA) values as high as 2g was observed in a station that is close to the epicenter of the first earthquake, Kahramanmaraş-Pazarcik. The strong ground motion data in terms of acceleration-time relationships measured during the three main earthquakes at the stations where maximum PGAs were recorded are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Acceleration time series of the earthquakes

The geometric means of spectral accelerations calculated making use of strong ground motion data for the records where the greatest PGAs were measured (AFAD, 2023) are presented in Table 1 for the building natural periods of 0.3, 1.0 and 3.0 seconds for the first earthquake. The design spectral acceleration values as per DD-1 and DD-2 ground motion levels are also calculated making use of the Earthquake Hazard Map for these three different period values and presented in the same table. The V_{s30} values in Table 1 corresponded to ZC soil class (very dense soil and soft rock) as per TBEC (2018). As seen in Table 1, the severity of the earthquake can be explained based on the measured spectral accelerations, which were significantly higher than the design spectral accelerations of DD-1 and DD-2 ground motion levels at certain periods. It should be noted that the structural design of buildings as per TBEC (2018) (excluding high-rise buildings and special structures such as schools, hospitals, and public buildings) is aimed at ensuring life safety performance under DD-2 ground motion level, but implicitly targets collapse prevention performance under DD-1. Figure 3 presents the 5% damped acceleration response spectra derived from the records obtained from Hatay and Kahramanmaraş. The response spectra in the figure are compared with the DD-1 and DD-2 design spectra. The labels E-W, N-S, and U-D indicate the records obtained from the same event but recorded in different directions (East-West, North-South, and Up-Down, respectively).

Table 1: Spectral accelerations, where the greatest PGAs were measured

Province	Station	V_{s30} (m/s)	Spectral Accelerations (g)								
			T=0.3 (s)			T=1.0 (s)			T=3.0 (s)		
			GM*	DD-2	DD-1	GM*	DD-2	DD-1	GM*	DD-2	DD-1
Hatay	3129	447	4.58	1.28	2.61	1.21	0.41	0.83	0.26	0.14	0.28
Kahramanmaraş	4614	541	3.90	1.35	2.56	0.42	0.44	0.83	0.12	0.15	0.28
Gaziantep	2718	-	1.33	1.59	3.14	0.67	0.52	1.02	0.24	0.17	0.34

*GM: Geometric mean of north-south and east-west components of spectral accelerations

Figure 3: 5%-damped acceleration response spectra is compared with respect to DD-1 and DD-2 design spectra (a) Hatay (Station no:3129, Defne), (b) Kahramanmaraş (Station no:4614, Pazarcik)

CHARACTERISTICS OF EXISTING BUILDINGS AND OBSERVED DAMAGES

Significant damages occurred in numerous buildings within the region. The severity of the earthquakes was of course effective on the extent of the damages. Nevertheless, as witnessed in previous earthquakes as well, the severity of seismic damage in these vulnerable structures primarily and mostly stemmed from poor and inadequate construction quality, including sub-standard workmanship and the use of low-quality building materials. Such deficiencies are commonly encountered in the existing building stock in Türkiye, especially in structures constructed before the year 2000. The construction year of buildings in Türkiye is supposed to be a rough indicator of the construction quality and seismic vulnerability. This is due to the fact that the 1998 Seismic Design Code of Türkiye introduced notable enhancements and design concepts, including capacity design approaches aimed at controlling the location of seismic damages in buildings. Furthermore, the catastrophic losses experienced during the 1999 Marmara Earthquakes prompted advancements in construction practices and inspection systems, leading to improved seismic performance of structures built after the year 2000. The widespread adoption of deformed bars and ready-mixed concrete became prevalent following developments in manufacturing technologies and technical documents. During our on-site inspections, structural damages from buildings, which were constructed before or after 2000 were collected. Unfortunately, it was observed that many buildings constructed after the year 2000 have been collapsed or heavily damaged due to construction malpractices in addition to severity of the earthquakes. This paper evaluates the observed damages by taking into account the specific characteristics of the structural systems, construction materials and construction details.

Distribution of Damage

The earthquakes have impacted mainly 11 provinces, encompassing an approximate area of 110,000 km², which includes a diverse range of building types. These include buildings surpassing traditional non-engineered structures, historical buildings, multi-story residential or office buildings and industrial structures, as well as public buildings, such as hospitals, schools and others. According to the assessment conducted by MoEUCC (2023), approximately 1.2 million RC buildings were inspected. Out of these, 1.0% were completely collapsed, 0.9% required immediate demolition, 6.4% suffered heavy damage, 1.8% experienced moderate damage, 25.7% had slight damage, and the rest 63.2% remained undamaged. It should be noted that the post-earthquake damage assessment was conducted based on the study by Ilki et al. (2021). The distribution of damage in inspected RC buildings per province can be seen in Figure 4a while the ratios of the damaged buildings together with maximum recorded PGAs as a function of g per province are presented in Figure 4b. It is important to note that the damage ratio is calculated by considering the proportion of heavily damaged buildings, those requiring immediate demolition, and completely collapsed structures in relation to the total number of inspected RC buildings. As depicted in Figure 4b, Hatay emerges as the most affected province, with approximately a quarter of the inspected buildings in the province collapsed, heavily damaged or requiring demolition.

Figure 4: (a) Distribution of damage level, (b) Damage ratios of the buildings per province

Figure 5 illustrates the distribution of inspected undamaged RC buildings and RC buildings with slight, moderate, heavy, immediate demolition, and collapsed damage levels categorized by their construction periods (MoEUCC, 2023). Although the year 2000 might seem like a significant turning point, Figure 5 clearly demonstrates that many buildings constructed after 2000 have also collapsed.

Figure 5: Damage distribution of RC buildings by construction year (data from MoEUCC, 2023)

Structural Damages and Causes of Failures

Recent seismic design documents, such as the current seismic design code of Türkiye (TBEC 2018), aim to ensure three essential requirements for buildings: sufficient stiffness, strength, and ductility. However, in the aftermath of the recent earthquakes, it has been observed that many severely damaged buildings in Türkiye failed to meet these requirements, as previously noted by Tapan et al. (2013) and Gurbuz et al. (2022). Figure 6 provides a visual representation of mid-rise RC buildings that did not satisfy the aforementioned requirements during the February 2023 Earthquakes. These buildings serve as general examples of structures that experienced significant damage due to their inability to meet the necessary stiffness, strength, and ductility criteria outlined in the seismic design documents.

Figure 6: (a) Collapsed, (b) Immediate demolition, (c) Heavily damaged mid-rise RC buildings

The severe damage observed in many buildings in the earthquake-affected region can be attributed to common defects that arose from the failure to fully adhere to seismic-resistant details outlined in recent seismic design codes in Türkiye (Ilki and Celep, 2012). Several notable deficiencies were identified, including the excessive spacing of stirrups beyond the maximum limits specified in design codes, the use of 90° stirrup hooks instead of the recommended 135° seismic hooks, and the absence of cross-ties. As a result, these stirrups were unable to effectively confine the concrete, which is crucial for achieving ductile behavior during the seismic events. Furthermore, the insufficient amount and detailing of

transverse reinforcement, coupled with low concrete strength, led to inadequate shear capacity and ultimately triggered shear failure in structural elements. Figure 7 provides examples illustrating these deficiencies in terms of the insufficient amount and detailing of transverse reinforcement in the affected RC buildings.

Figure 7: Insufficient transverse reinforcement. (a) Column, (b) Joint, (c) Shear wall

Seismic codes are implemented to regulate the levels of axial stress in columns to ensure their ductile behavior. However, in the case of damaged buildings, the columns experienced elevated axial stress levels due to various factors such as poor concrete quality, smaller cross-sections, and additional loads that were not considered during the design phase. The existing high axial stress levels, resulting from gravitational loads, were further increased by the horizontal and vertical components of the seismic motion. These combined effects led to a brittle response of the columns, resulting in premature damage characterized by concrete cover spalling, core concrete crushing, and longitudinal bar buckling (Figure 7a). Columns are critical vertical structural elements, and their failure can cause severe damage or even the collapse of the entire structure. To ensure column strength, capacity design principles were first introduced in RC design with the issuance of the TSDC (1998). The current design approach for moment-resisting frame systems aims to form plastic hinges at beam end regions rather than in columns and joints, which is achieved by establishing a strength hierarchy among beams and columns at the joints. However, during site visits, it was observed that seismic damages were mostly concentrated in columns rather than beams, which increased the risk of pancake-type collapses (Figure 6a).

Short column failures were also noted during the field investigations. Improper arrangement of infill walls or stairs resulted in shortened effective column lengths, making these columns stiffer. Consequently, the seismic loads transferred to these short columns were exceptionally high, causing them to be unable to withstand the significant shear forces, resulting in severe damage (Figure 8a).

Figure 8: (a) Short column, (b) Structural system deficiencies observed in buildings constructed after year 2000

In buildings constructed after 2000, numerous deficiencies have been identified in their structural systems; including irregularities in both vertical and horizontal directions, inadequate amount of shear walls, frame discontinuities, extensive use of joist slabs with shallow beams, and use of shear walls or rectangular columns with their strong direction aligned in one direction of the building only. Moreover, despite use of closely-spaced stirrups, there are still issues regarding insufficient detailing of transverse reinforcement, such as widespread absence of crossties, and use of ties with 90° hooks (or with 90° hook at one end 135° at the other end), which result in poor confinement and insufficient flexural ductility. Although most of these buildings have undergone structural design and have been built with relatively good construction/material quality, under such large ground motion demands experienced during these earthquakes, these standalone deficiencies have also led to high-level damage, and in some cases, total collapse of relatively new buildings (Figure 8b).

FIBER REINFORCED POLYMERS FOR STRENGTHENING OF RC STRUCTURAL MEMBERS

The February 2023 earthquakes had devastating consequences, such as the collapse or severe damage of huge number of existing buildings and tremendous amount of casualties. These events highlighted the urgent need for seismic upgrading of existing structures, particularly, due to the prevalence of sub-standard buildings or buildings with individual (e.g., detailing) deficiencies. In this context, FRPs have emerged as an attractive solution due to their high strength, lightweight composition, excellent durability (corrosion resistance), and ease of application for enhancing the resilience of buildings, enabling them to better withstand and maintain functionality after seismic events. This section aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the potential use of FRPs in seismic strengthening. Drawing upon previous experimental studies, various seismic strengthening methods utilizing FRPs will be summarized. Additionally, practical applications of these methods in response to the damages observed in recent earthquakes in Türkiye will be highlighted.

FRPs are commonly utilized in the field of RC member strengthening through a technique known as externally bonded reinforcement (EBR). This involves using FRP fabrics and epoxy resins to attach the FRPs to the concrete substrate. One of the primary applications of FRPs as EBR is as shear reinforcement in columns that lack sufficient stirrups, thereby, ensuring a ductile flexural response. As discussed earlier (Figure 7), deficiencies in transverse reinforcement detailing can lead to severe damages in columns leading to a brittle failure. To prevent such a brittle damage mechanism, FRPs can be employed to wrap the columns, providing confinement to the inner concrete and significantly increasing the ductility of the member. According to ACI 440.2R-17 (2017) and TBEC (2018), the use of FRP jacketing for rectangular concrete structural members is not recommended if their aspect ratio (h/b) exceeds 1.5 or 2.5, respectively (particularly for strength enhancement). However, in the study conducted by Ghatte et al. (2019) (Figure 9a) and Akgun et al. (2010), notable improvements in ductility were achieved for sub-standard columns with an extended rectangular cross-section with aspect ratios (h/b) of two and three. In the study conducted by Ghatte et al. (2019), the seismic performances of six full-scale sub-standard columns with extended rectangular cross-sections ($h/b=2.0$) were investigated. The columns were subjected to reversed cyclic and axial loading both before and after retrofitting with carbon FRP (CFRP) jacketing (Figure 9a). The study examined the effects of different parameters, including the number of CFRP layers (one or two) and the axial load ratio ($0.20 f_c b h$ or $0.35 f_c b h$). For columns subjected to an axial load corresponding to $0.20 f_c b h$, the ultimate drift ratio increased from 3% to 4% and 7.5% with one and two layers of external CFRP jacketing, respectively. For columns subjected to an axial load corresponding to $0.35 f_c b h$, the ultimate drift ratio increased from 1.5% to 3% and 5% for one and two layers of external CFRP jacketing, respectively. These results highlight the effectiveness of external CFRP jacketing in enhancing the seismic performance of sub-standard columns, particularly in terms of ductility.

Figure 9: Views of test specimens (a) Ghatte et al. (2019), (b) Ilki et al. (2018)

FRP wrapping of wall-like RC columns have been also studied by Hosny et al. (2001) before, where they tested 12 rectangular RC columns under axial loading. The columns were confined using CFRP strips. The researchers have shown that the limited effectiveness of CFRP wrapping in case of wall-like columns could be improved by transforming the shape of the cross-section to an elliptical one (like the actual application in Figure 10a). In another study by Ghatte et al. (2016), the seismic behavior of full-scale sub-standard rectangular RC columns retrofitted with CFRP jacketing and external steel ties was investigated. The test results indicated that the inclusion of external steel ties along with FRP jacketing can significantly enhance the ductility and energy dissipation capabilities of the wall-like columns by increasing the effectively confined concrete area. An example illustrating the FRP wrapping of wall-like RC columns can be seen in Figure 10b.

Figure 10: FRP wrapping for wide columns (a) Transforming shape of the cross section to elliptical, (b) Usage of steel cross-ties (Photos by courtesy of Rise Engineering)

Furthermore, the effectiveness of FRP jacketing in improving the ductility and shear capacity of sub-standard columns has been convincingly demonstrated in an experimental study conducted on two full-scale three-story RC frame structures by Ilki et al. (2018). These structures, one representing the original as-built condition and the other retrofitted with FRP, were identical in terms of design geometry, material quality, and seismic deficiencies. In the retrofitted building, the upper and lower ends of the first-story columns were wrapped with 5 plies of CFRP, while the end regions of the second-story columns were wrapped with 3 plies of CFRP, each with a height of 60 cm. Additionally, two plies of CFRP sheets were applied to the remaining height of the columns to enhance their shear capacity. During the cyclic loading, the reference building (without retrofitting) experienced a significant loss of lateral strength starting at a drift ratio of 0.9%. The degradation continued dramatically until a first-story drift ratio of 1.45%, at which the building collapsed abruptly. In contrast, the retrofitted building exhibited a much-improved response. The loading continued until approximately a 15% drift ratio at which test had to be terminated due to stroke limitations of the actuators (Figure 9b). These results highlight the substantial benefits of FRP jacketing for enhancing the seismic performance of sub-standard RC buildings, particularly in terms of ductility.

As observed during the recent February 2023 Earthquakes, short columns, which are commonly found in construction practice, are prone to shear damage due to deficiencies such as low-strength concrete and insufficient transverse reinforcement (Figure 8a). Retrofitting these columns becomes crucial to prevent adverse consequences during seismic events. A study conducted by Bedirhanoglu et al. (2022) investigated the seismic response of FRP-retrofitted low-strength RC short columns with or without pre-damage. The research involved testing of 11 short column specimens representing old and deficient RC buildings (Figure 11a). The test results revealed that retrofitting with FRP significantly improved the strength and displacement ductility of the columns. The strength increased from 36% to 79%, and the displacement ductility increased from 11% to 35%, for different retrofitting schemes. As expected, the initial stiffness of the columns was not significantly affected by the retrofitting process. Notably, both CFRP and glass FRP (GFRP) sheets demonstrated effective enhancement in the response of the columns, and the behavior of repaired and retrofitted pre-damaged specimens was similar to that of the strengthened undamaged ones. These findings emphasize the importance of retrofitting short columns, particularly in sub-standard RC buildings.

Post-earthquake reconnaissance studies have consistently shown that beam-column joints in sub-standard RC buildings often fail to withstand the forces and deformations imposed during severe seismic events (Figure 7b). Consequently, preventing premature failure of joints is a fundamental principle in modern seismic design to ensure that the framing members can fully utilize their capacity. The effectiveness of CFRP in retrofitting beam-column joints was investigated in a study by Cosgun et al. (2019), which utilized full-scale three-dimensional RC frames representative of structures built in Türkiye before the year 2000 (Figure 11b). The experimental study involved quasi-static testing of four 3D frames, with two serving as reference specimens and the other two retrofitted with CFRP sheets. The introduction of FRP retrofitting to the beam-column joints significantly enhanced both the lateral load and displacement capacities so that the ductility of the system exhibited a substantial improvement, and the lateral load capacity was sustained up to an 8.0% lateral drift ratio.

Figure 11: Views of test specimens (a) Bedirhanoglu et al. (2022), (b) Cosgun et al. (2019)

In addition to the frequently used external confinement method, which mainly enhances the shear capacity and ductility, there are retrofitting methods that could be used for increasing the flexural capacity of structural elements using near surface mounted (NSM) FRP rods or pultruded strips without altering the original dimension of the structural members. The study conducted by Goksu et al. (2012) focused on investigating the use of CFRP reinforcement for the flexural retrofit of sub-standard RC columns under reversed cyclic loading conditions. In this study, CFRP reinforcement was applied in the longitudinal direction and anchored to the footing to enhance the flexural strength of the columns. In addition, the specimens were externally jacketed with FRP sheets in the transverse direction to prevent buckling and debonding of CFRP reinforcement (Figure 12). The findings demonstrated that the retrofitting technique effectively enhanced the flexural capacity even at large cyclic drifts.

Furthermore, a recent study by Seyhan et al. (2023) explored the contribution of single or hybrid use of different types of longitudinal FRP bars (such as aramid FRP, GFRP and CFRP) in the seismic flexural retrofit of sub-standard RC columns, following a similar approach as Goksu et al. (2012) by adding longitudinal FRP reinforcement and applying CFRP sheets in the transverse direction. The results indicated that the lateral load capacities of the retrofitted columns were significantly enhanced by introducing longitudinal FRP reinforcement. These studies highlight the effectiveness of using NSM FRP rods or pultruded strips for flexural retrofitting, enabling the increase of flexural capacity without modifying the original dimensions of the structural elements. By combining longitudinal and transverse FRP reinforcement, it is possible to enhance the overall seismic performance of sub-standard RC members and mitigating against issues such as buckling or debonding of reinforcement, or shear damage, in addition to improving the flexural response.

Figure 12: Flexural strengthening through FRPs (a) Installation of CFRP laminates, (b) Wrapping with CFRP sheets in transverse direction (Goksu et al., 2012)

CONCLUSIONS

Starting from February 6th, 2023, a series of three devastating earthquakes struck the south-eastern part of Türkiye, resulting in significant damage to the built environment. According to MoEUCC (2023), out of 1.2 million inspected RC buildings, 1.0% completely collapsed, 0.9% required immediate demolition, and 6.4% suffered heavy damage. It is crucial to gain a deeper understanding of the factors influencing the performance of these seismically vulnerable structures, as their collapse contributes significantly to earthquake-related losses. Based on site observations, several conclusions and recommendations can be summarized as follows:

- The spectral accelerations calculated were remarkably higher than one would predict for DD-1 (2475 years return period) and DD-2 (475 years return period) ground motion levels for a wide range of building periods.
- Recurring pattern of the similar construction errors as in the previous earthquakes were observed. The most common problems were related with poor construction practice (in terms of workmanship, particularly in reinforcement detailing and concreting), whereas some poorly arranged structural systems were also observed due to deficiencies in design phase.
- Although capacity design principles and enhanced reinforcement detailing have been introduced since the early 2000s and the material quality has been improved in general, the occurrence of pancake-type collapses of structures built after the year 2000 due to the persistence of soft story, weak story conditions and poor detailing indicates the lack of effective implementation of these principles and poor inspection system.

The building stock of the region is somehow representative of that of the whole country. Strengthening this building stock rapidly and efficiently is of paramount importance. In this regards, the use of FRPs for retrofitting stands out due to its numerous advantages. It should be pointed out that the research and successful practical applications of FRP retrofitting have accumulated over the past 20-30 years, reaching a certain level of maturity, to be effectively used for reduction of losses against future earthquakes.

REFERENCES

- Akgun, D., Demir, C., Ilki, A., “Axial behavior of FRP jacketed extended rectangular members constructed with low strength concrete,” *5th International Conference on FRP Composites in Civil Engineering*, Beijing, September, 2010.
- American Concrete Institute (ACI). (2017). *ACI 440.2R-17: Guide for design and construction of externally bonded FRP systems for strengthening concrete structures*. Farmington Hills, Michigan.
- Bedirhanoglu, I., Ilki, A., & Triantafillou, T. C. (2022). Seismic behavior of repaired and externally FRP-jacketed short columns built with extremely low-strength concrete. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 26(1), 04021068. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CC.1943-5614.0001179](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CC.1943-5614.0001179)
- Cosgun, C., Cömert, M., Demir, C., & İlki, A. (2019). Seismic retrofit of joints of a full-scale 3D reinforced concrete frame with FRP composites. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 23(2), 04019004. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CC.1943-5614.0000923](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CC.1943-5614.0000923)
- Disaster and Emergency Management Presidency of Ministry of Interior Affairs of Türkiye (AFAD). Accessed on April 13, 2023. <http://www.afad.gov.tr>
- Earthquake Engineering Research Institute (EERI). (2023). *February 6, 2023 Türkiye earthquakes: Report on geoscience and engineering impacts*. <https://10.18118/G6PM34>
- Emre, Ö., Duman, T. Y., Özalp, S., Şaroğlu, F., Olgun, Ş., Elmacı, H., & Çan, T. (2018). Active fault database of Turkey. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 16(8), 3229-3275. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-016-0041-2>
- Ghate, H. F., Comert, M., Demir, C., & Ilki, A. (2016). Seismic performance of full-scale FRP retrofitted substandard RC columns loaded in the weak direction. In: Monti, G., Martinelli, E. (eds) *Applied Mechanics and Materials* (Vol. 847, pp. 347–353). Trans Tech Publications, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/amm.847.347>
- Ghate, H. F., Comert, M., Demir, C., Akbaba, M., & Ilki, A. (2019). Seismic retrofit of full-scale substandard extended rectangular RC columns through CFRP jacketing: Test results and design recommendations. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 23(1), 04018071. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CC.1943-5614.0000907](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CC.1943-5614.0000907)
- Goksu, C., Polat, A., & Ilki, A. (2012). Attempt for seismic retrofit of existing substandard RC members under reversed cyclic flexural effects. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 16(3), 286-299. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CC.1943-5614.0000256](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CC.1943-5614.0000256)
- Gurbuz, T., Cengiz, A., Kolemenoglu, S., Demir, C., & Ilki, A. (2022). Damages and failures of structures in Izmir (Turkey) during the October 30, 2020 Aegean Sea earthquake. *Journal of Earthquake Engineering*, 1-42. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632469.2022.2086186>
- Hosny, A., Shahin, H., Abdelrahman, A., & El-Afandy, T. (2001). Strengthening of rectangular RC columns using CFRP. In: Burgoyne, C. J. (ed) *Proceedings of 5th International Conference on Fibre-Reinforced Plastics for Reinforced Concrete Structures* (pp. 773-782). Cambridge, UK.
- Ilki, A., & Celep, Z. (2012). Earthquakes, existing buildings and seismic design codes in Turkey. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, 37, 365-380. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-012-0183-8>

Ilki, A., Tore, E., Demir, C., & Comert, M. (2018). Seismic performance of a full-scale FRP retrofitted sub-standard RC building. In: Ptilakis, K. (eds) *Recent Advances in Earthquake Engineering in Europe. ECEE 2018. Geotechnical, Geological and Earthquake Engineering, vol 46*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-75741-4_22

Ilki, A., Halici, O.F., Comert, M., & Demir, C. (2021). The modified post-earthquake damage assessment methodology for TCIP (TCIP-DAM-2020). In: Akkar, S., Ilki, A., Goksu, C., Erdik, M. (eds) *Advances in Assessment and Modeling of Earthquake Loss*. Springer Tracts in Civil Engineering. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-68813-4_5

Ministry of Environment, Urbanisation and Climate Change (MoEUCC) of Türkiye. Accessed on May 10, 2023. <https://csb.gov.tr>

Seyhan, E. C., Goksu, C., Saribas, I., & Ilki, A. (2023). Hybrid use of externally embedded FRP reinforcement for seismic retrofitting of substandard RC columns. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 27(3), 04023022. <https://doi.org/10.1061/JCCOF2.CCENG-3906>

Strategy and Budget Office of Presidency of Türkiye (SBO). (2023). *2023 Kahramanmaraş and Hatay earthquakes report*. <https://www.sbb.gov.tr/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/2023-Kahramanmaras-and-Hatay-Earthquakes-Report.pdf>

Tapan, M., Comert, M., Demir, C., Sayan, Y., Orakcal, K., & Ilki, A. (2013). Failures of structures during the October 23, 2011 Tabanlı (Van) and November 9, 2011 Edremit (Van) earthquakes in Turkey. *Engineering Failure Analysis*, 34, 606-628. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfailanal.2013.02.013>

Türkiye Building Earthquake Code (TBEC). (2018). Official Gazette of Republic of Türkiye, 30364, 18 March 2018.

Turkish Seismic Design Code (TSDC). (1998). Official Gazette of Republic of Türkiye, 23390, 2 July 1998.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to express their gratitude to Turkish Natural Catastrophe Insurance Pool (DASK), Ministry of Interior Affairs Disaster and Emergency Management Authority (AFAD) and Turkish Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change, and Dr. Cem Demir for their support.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.